

Green Synthesis and Multifunctional Bioactivity of *Vitis vinifera* Seed-Mediated Silver Nanoparticles Against MDR Uropathogens and Breast Cancer Cells

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Abstract

Background: Green nanotechnology offers a sustainable approach towards biocompatible nanoparticle synthesis for various biomedical applications. **Objective:** Synthesis of silver nanoparticles (VV-AgNPs) using grape seed extract (*Vitis vinifera*). Characterization of the synthesized nanoparticles in terms of their physical and chemical properties, evaluation of their antibacterial activity, and their cytotoxic potential against breast cancer cells. **Methodology:** Prepare a grape seed extract for green synthesis of silver nanoparticles. The nanoparticles were characterized physicochemically and evaluated for antibacterial, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities using standard microbiological, cell-based, spectroscopic, and biochemical assays. **Results:** The morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles was spherical, well dispersed, and less than 70 nm in diameter with several absorption peaks in 430–480 nm. The antibacterial activity of the VV-AgNPs was found to be very effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K. pneumoniae*), while *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) was relatively resistant. Additionally, cytotoxicity studies indicated selective inhibition of MCF-7 breast cancer cells ($IC_{50}=157.3 \mu\text{g/mL}$) with relatively low toxicity to normal fibroblast cells. The anti-inflammatory evaluations supported that the low and middle concentrations did not enhance COX-2 expression. **Conclusion:** The biosynthesized nanoparticles possessed structural properties. The VV-AgNPs stable biocompatible nanoparticles with notable bioactivity for possible microbial and anti-cancer applications.

Keywords: Antibacterial activity, anticancer activity, anti-inflammatory effect, green synthesis, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), *Vitis vinifera* seed extract.

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Introduction

The field of nanotechnology has developed multifaceted disciplines connecting chemistry, biology, and materials science [1–3]. Materials demonstrate properties quite different from the bulk when they are of nano size, an order of 1–100 nm. High surface-to-volume ratio, tuneable shapes and enhanced reactivity lead to new optical, catalytic and biological qualities [4]. Nanoparticles have provided innumerable advantages, translating to many potential biomedical applications such as drug delivery at a targeting site, imaging, biosensors, and cancer therapy due to their controllable size and surface chemistry [5–7].

Among various types of Nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have received special attention because of their unique antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer activities [8–10]. Their biological effects are ascribed to several synergistic mechanisms in addition to their nanoscale size and large surface area. These include disruption of cell membranes upon adhesion to the cell surface, interactions with protein and DNA, as well as the induction and promotion subsequently of

oxidative stress, causing apoptosis or death of microbial cells [11]. Accordingly, AgNPs are widely used in medical coatings, wound dressings, biosensors, and drug delivery systems by virtue of the release of ionic silver, their surface properties, or due to the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [12–14]. Nevertheless, traditional synthetic procedures of such Nanoparticles usually require the usage of toxic reactants and complicated operations without consideration of environment-friendliness and biological compatibility [15].

These limitations have prompted the development of a green route that is simple, nontoxic, and environmentally friendly to produce NPs using natural reducing and stabilizing agents. Among biological approaches, plant-mediated synthesis is particularly attractive due to its simplicity, rapid reaction kinetics, and environmental compatibility [16]. Phytochemicals from plant extracts, which are of many classes including phenolics, flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids, and organic acids, play a vital role in the reduction of silver ions to nanosilver as well as capping and stabilizing the formed nanoparticles [17]. The surface modification

by these biomolecules improves the bioactivity and stability of AgNPs, demonstrating a synergistic relationship between metallic and phytochemical components [18].

Vitis vinifera (vv) (grape) seeds are a rich natural source of phenolic compounds, especially catechins, gallic acid, and proanthocyanidins, showing strong antioxidant and medicinal effects [19]. These biologically active molecules are capable of reducing the silver ions and stabilizing the nanoparticles formed [20]. Additionally, the phytochemical capping of *Vitis vinifera* seed-produced AgNPs increases their biocompatibility and can increase their antibacterial and anticancer activity [21]. Although green-synthesized nanomaterials have gained interest globally, there are limited comprehensive studies on the multi-functional bioactivity of grape seed (GS)-derived AgNPs specifically against multidrug-resistant uropathogens and breast cancer cells.

In this study, silver nanoparticles (VV-AgNPs) were synthesized using *Vitis vinifera* (VV) seed extract as a reducing and capping agent. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized for their physicochemical properties and evaluated for their antibacterial activity against multidrug-resistant urinary pathogens and their cytotoxic potential against breast cancer cells. This study aims to provide an eco-friendly and biologically potent nanosystem.

Materials and Methods

All of the reagents used in this work were analytical grade and were directly used as received without further purification. All experiments were performed using deionized water. The experiments were conducted on standard laboratory apparatus, such as an autoclave (Aquarius, UK), centrifuge machine (Hettich, Germany), spectrophotometer (PG, India), shaker incubator (Sartorius, Germany), hotplate stirrer (Labinco, the Netherlands), and ultrasonic device (Fuyang, China).

Preparation of *Vitis vinifera* (Grape Seed) Extract

Vitis vinifera Seeds (VV) were collected from the local market and transported to the laboratory. The seeds were washed well with tap water and then rinsed with deionized water (DW) to get rid of the adhering dust or impurities. They were dried at room temperature and milled into fine powder by an electric grinder. The aqueous extract was prepared by mixing 4 g of the powdered seed material in a glass flask, adding 100 mL of DW, and refluxing for 30 min at 100 °C, and then filtering to isolate the solid residue from the filtrate, which was allowed to cool at room temperature. The extract obtained was preserved at 4 °C for further experimentation.

Green Synthesis of VV-AgNPs

Green plant-mediated synthesis of (VV-AgNPs) was carried out. Once the aqueous extract of *Vitis vinifera* seeds was prepared, 300 mL of the extract was slowly mixed with 100 mL of AgNO₃ (1 mM) solution under continuous stirring at 45 °C for 30 min. The solution was kept at 37 °C for seven days until the color of the solution changed from light yellow to dark brown, which affirmed the formation of AgNPs. The product was then centrifuged at 4000 rpm (15 min), washed four times with deionized water, dried at room temperature (r.t.), and stored at 4 °C for further use.

Characterization of VV-AgNPs

VV-AgNPs were described by means of several analytical techniques. The Thermo Biomate 5 for UV-Visible spectroscopy was used to obtain the absorption spectra of VV-AgNPs in the range of 200–800 nm. The FTIR profiles of the plant extract and the synthesized VV-AgNPs were compared to determine the functional group reduction of Ag⁺ ions into metallic silver (Ag⁰). The crystal structure of VV-AgNPs was studied by X-ray diffraction (XRD, Philips PW1730) in the 2θ range from 10° to 80°. Surface morphology of the nanoparticles was studied by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM; TESCAN MIRA3), whereas

particle size distribution was approximately analyzed through ImageJ software. Elemental analysis was conducted by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), and its stability as well as zeta potential were measured on a zetasizer (HORIBA SZ-100).

Antibacterial Activity of VV-AgNPs

The antibacterial activity of the synthesized VV-AgNPs was evaluated against four uropathogenic bacteria, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *P. aeruginosa* using the Kirby–Bauer disk diffusion method on Mueller–Hinton agar according to CLSI guidelines [22]. A stock solution of VV-AgNPs (1000 µg/mL) was prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and sonicated for 20 min at 20 kHz. Serial twofold dilutions (1000–62.5 µg/mL) were prepared. Bacterial suspensions were adjusted to the 0.5 McFarland standard and spread onto Mueller–Hinton agar plates. Wells (6 mm) were made using a sterile cork borer and filled with 100 µL of each dilution. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h, and inhibition zones were measured. Clear zones indicated bacterial sensitivity, while the absence of inhibition denoted resistance.

Anticancer Activity of VV-AgNPs

The cytotoxic potential of VV-AgNPs was evaluated using the MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) assay against normal human dermal fibroblast (HdFn) and breast cancer (MCF-7) cell lines. Cell suspensions (1×10⁴–1×10⁶ cells/mL) were seeded into 96-well microtiter plates containing 200 µL of culture medium per well and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. Subsequently, the cells were treated with 200 µL (VV-AgNPs) solutions prepared in twofold serial dilutions (500, 250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/mL) and incubated for an additional 48 h under identical conditions. After treatment, 10 µL of MTT reagent was added to each well, and the plates were incubated for 4 h to allow the formation of formazan crystals. The supernatant was then carefully removed, and 100 µL of DMSO was added to solubilize the crystals. Absorbance was recorded at 575 nm using an ELISA microplate reader (Bio-Rad, Germany). Cell viability (%) was calculated using the equation:

$$\text{Viability (\%)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{control}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀), representing the concentration required to inhibit 50% of cell viability, was subsequently determined.

Antioxidant Activity of VV-AgNPs

The antioxidant ability of the prepared VV-AgNPs was measured by using a stable DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay based on Al-Saffar *et al.*, protocol, with minor modifications [23]. A Serial two-fold dilution of VV-AgNPs in different test tubes was performed at concentrations of 500, 250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/mL. To the different dilution, 3 mL methanol–DMSO mixture (9:1, v/v), and 0.3 mL DPPH solution (0.1 mg/mL) were mixed. The solutions were lightly agitated and kept in the dark at room temperature for 1 h. The absorbance at 517 nm was read by an ELISA microplate reader after incubation. The MeOH–DMSO–DPPH mixture without nanoparticles was used as the negative control, and ascorbic acid as a standard reference. % of DPPH radical scavenging activity was determined as follows:

$$\text{Scavenging \%} = \frac{\text{Control absorbance} - \text{Sample absorbance}}{\text{Control absorbance}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Anti-Inflammatory Activity of VV-AgNPs

The anti-inflammatory activity of the synthesized VV-AgNPs was assessed by evaluating their effect on cyclooxygenase-2 (COX₂) enzyme expression. The assay was performed according to the method described by Ahn *et al.*, with slight modifications [24]. Briefly, cells were

seeded into 96-well microtiter plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells per well and incubated overnight at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. After incubation, the culture medium was replaced with fresh medium containing VV-AgNPs at different concentrations (500, 250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/mL), and the cells were further incubated for 24 h under identical conditions. Following treatment, cells were harvested, and COX₂ enzyme expression levels were quantified using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Untreated cells cultured in medium alone served as the control group.

Results and Discussion

UV-Vis Spectroscopic

The UV-Vis spectrum of AgNPs (Fig. 1) demonstrated several absorption peaks, the primary peak at approximately 430 nm with a secondary shoulder at around 480 nm [25]. These peaks are attributed to the SPR of AgNPs, indicating their efficient green synthesis with VV seed extract. The multiple bands of absorption could be due to very small differences in the size or morphology of nanoparticles and their interaction with some residual phytochemicals [26]. The noticeable change in the color of the solution from light yellow to brown is clear evidence for both the formation and stability of VV-AgNPs.

Figure 1: UV-Vis absorption spectrum of VV-AgNPs

FTIR Spectra

The FTIR of VV seed extract and the prepared VV-AgNPs are depicted in (Fig. 2). The extract was characterized by significant absorption bands at 3400 cm^{-1} (O-H stretching hydroxyl or phenolic groups), about 1620 cm^{-1} (C=O or C=C stretching vibrations), and in the region of $1000\text{--}1100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O stretching) [27]. After the formation of nanoparticles, shifts in peak positions and intensity reduction were observed as verification for the involvement of these functional groups in the Ag⁺ reduced to Ag⁰ process and in stabilization of the nanoparticles. These results demonstrate that phenolic, hydroxyl (OH), and carbonyl (C=O) groups in VV extract acted as natural reducing and capping agents in the biosynthesis of VV-AgNPs [28].

SEM Analysis

The FESEM image of the biosynthesized VV-AgNPs (Fig. 3) shows predominantly spherical-shaped NPs with a fair degree of agglomeration and non-homogeneous surface morphology. The diameters of the particles are in the scale of 36-59 nm with an average diameter of about 46.6 nm, which shows a narrow size distribution. Some of the nanoparticles show a mild irregular or rough surface, especially at the 200 nm magnification scale, perhaps due to some agglomeration and/or an incomplete surface covering of phytochemicals from VV seed extract [29,30]. This roughness could be produced by the presence of the naturally formed capping layer of both polyphenols and proteins, which may limit over-aggregation and promote particle

stabilization. It is well known that diversity in particle size of biosynthesized AgNPs is a result of interaction between the concentration of reducing phytochemicals, availability of silver ions, and reaction parameters [31]. In general, the FESEM image supports that the VV-AgNPs are well formed and moderately distributed, as well as having a similar morphology to other plant-mediated silver nanoparticles reported.

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of (VV) extract (top) and VV-AgNPs (bottom)

Figure 3: FESEM micrograph of VV-AgNPs

EDX Analysis

The elemental analysis of prepared VV-AgNPs was analyzed using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), and is shown in (Fig. 4). Clearly observed characteristic peaks indicated that silver was the primary elemental constituent of the synthesized nanoparticles. Oxygen (O) and chlorine (Cl) signals were also observed with a higher intensity than the background; this could be due to surface-adsorbed biomolecules or to residual ionic species of the synthesis medium. Minor peaks for elements Na, K, Ca, and Mg were observed, probably due to the presence of phytochemicals in the *Vitis vinifera* seed extract [32]. This total silver content of about 35.5 wt. %, indicating that Ag was the predominant element of the nanoparticle composition and further confirming successful green synthetic VV-AgNPs.

Figure 4: EDX Analysis of VV-AgNPs

XRD Analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) of synthesized VV-AgNPs (Fig. 5) revealed a crystalline nature. The diffractogram exhibited well-defined and intense peaks at approximately $2\theta = 27.8^\circ, 32.2^\circ, 35.1^\circ, 46.3^\circ, 54.7^\circ, 57.4^\circ, 64.5^\circ,$ and 76.8° , corresponding to the (210), (122), (111), (200), (142), (241), (220), and (311), respectively, the characteristic planes of (FCC) AgNPs (JCPDS 04-0783) [33]. The sharpness and intensity of these reflections suggest that biosynthesized nanoparticles are highly crystalline in nature. Minute unindexed peaks are assignable to organic residues or phytochemicals, i.e., molecules present in VV extract and still attached to the nanoparticle surface even after washing [34]. The absence of any impurities or peaks related to silver oxide is also seen, suggesting phase purity of the synthesized AgNPs.

Figure 5: X-ray diffraction pattern analysis of biosynthesized VV-AgNPs

Antibacterial Activity of VV-AgNPs

The antibacterial activity of VV-AgNPs was tested against four multidrug-resistant uropathogenic bacteria by the agar well diffusion method. As shown (Fig. 6 & Table 1), the VV-AgNPs a significant dose-dependent inhibitory effect. Inhibitory zones were observed for *E. coli* (B, 20mm), followed by *S. aureus* (A, 18 mm), *K. pneumoniae* (C, 16 mm) *P. aeruginosa* (D, 16 mm) at the highest concentration level of (1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The inhibition zones gradually decreased with the decrease in concentration, suggesting that antibacterial activity was

decreasing. At a concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, VV-AgNPs also exerted mild inhibitory activity on *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae* with no response against *P. aeruginosa*. Lower concentration (250–62.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) showed lower inhibition zones, and *P. aeruginosa* was fully resistant to it. No suppression was observed in the DMSO control, indicating that antibacterial activity was associated only with VV-AgNPs. These results suggest that VV-AgNPs have strong antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, moderate antibacterial activity against *K. pneumoniae*, and weak antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa*. This variable sensitivity is probably due to differences in the phylogenetic and biochemical characteristics of bacteria. The dense lipopolysaccharide-rich outer membrane of *P. aeruginosa* restricts nanoparticle penetration and supports multidrug resistance, while its efflux pumps and detoxifying enzymes reduce oxidative stress induced by Ag^+ ions and reactive oxygen species (ROS) [35–37]. In contrast, *E. coli* and *S. aureus* are more vulnerable because of weaker cellular defense systems, higher membrane permeability, and increased nanoparticle adhesion [38]. The antibacterial mechanism of VV-AgNPs involves several concurrent processes, including nanoparticle attachment to the bacterial surface, disruption of membrane integrity, generation of ROS, leakage of intracellular contents, and inhibition of DNA replication through Ag^+ binding to sulfur- and phosphorus-containing biomolecules. Additionally, the plant-derived capping of polyphenols and tannins on VV-AgNPs, while improving particle stability and preventing aggregation, may reduce Ag^+ ion release, resulting in slightly lower bactericidal potency compared with more reactive AgNPs reported in other studies [39]. These findings are consistent with previous literature on green-synthesized AgNPs, where inhibition strength varied depending on nanoparticle morphology, size, stability, and the type of plant extract used. Smaller and less-stabilized AgNPs generally exhibit higher surface energy, faster Ag^+ ion release, and stronger interaction with bacterial membranes, enhancing their bactericidal effect, whereas strongly capped or aggregated particles display reduced activity [40]. Therefore, the antibacterial behavior of VV-AgNPs against MDR uropathogens can be attributed to a synergistic interplay between their physicochemical properties, the phytochemical composition of the VV extract, and the inherent structural resistance of the bacterial cell envelope.

Figure 6: Antibacterial activity of VV-AgNPs against (A) *S. aureus*, (B) *E. coli*, (C) *K. pneumoniae*, and (D) *P. aeruginosa*. Wells: 1 (1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), 2 (500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), 3 (250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), 4 (125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), 5 (62.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and 6 (DMSO control)

Table 1: Average inhibition zone diameters (mm) of VV-AgNPs against tested bacterial strains at different concentrations

No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Pathogen growth inhibitory zone (mm)			
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
1	1000	18	20	16	16
2	500	17	16	14	0
3	250	16	16	14	0
4	125	14	15	13	0
5	62.5	12	15	11	0
6	Control (DMSO)	0	0	0	0

Anticancer Activity of VV-AgNPs

The anticancer potential of VV-AgNPs was assessed against MCF-7 breast cancer cells and normal HdFn fibroblast cells using the MTT assay. As illustrated in (Fig. 7), a clear concentration-dependent decrease in cell viability was observed for both cell lines. MCF-7 cells exhibited higher sensitivity to VV-AgNPs, with an IC₅₀ value of 157.3 µg/mL, compared to HdFn cells (without IC₅₀), indicating a selective cytotoxic effect toward cancer cells while maintaining lower toxicity in normal cells. The cytotoxicity of VV-AgNPs may be attributed to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), mitochondrial dysfunction, and the activation of apoptosis pathways in malignant cells [41]. These effects are consistent with previously reported studies on green-synthesized AgNPs [42]. For instance, AgNPs synthesized using shilajit extract exhibited potent cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cells, with IC₅₀ values of 11.50 µg/mL and 16.26 µg/mL after 24 and 48 hours, respectively [43]. Similarly, marine-derived *Fusarium equiseti*-based AgNPs showed strong antioxidant capacity (IC₅₀ = 56.98 µg/mL) and significant cytotoxicity against MCF-7 cells (IC₅₀ = 24.38 µg/mL) [44]. The higher IC₅₀ value reported in the present study as compared with previous workers may be due to a difference in nanoparticle size, shape, and the presence of phytochemicals from capping *Vitis vinifera* seed nanoparticles. These properties predominantly affect cellular uptake, surface charge, and oxidative reactivity. The bigger and more stable the nanoparticles are, the lower they release Ag⁺ ions, which exhibit only mild cytotoxicity with selectivity. However, its smaller highly reactive nanoparticles provoke more potent oxidative stress and promote apoptosis faster [45]. Therefore, VV-AgNPs exhibit biocompatible behavior with selective anticancer activity, offering a great promise for the therapeutics where controlled activity is required and reduced side toxicity in normal tissues is desired.

Figure 7: Cytotoxicity of VV-AgNPs against MCF-7 breast cancer and HdFn normal fibroblast cells

Anti-Inflammatory Activity of VV-AgNPs

The cyclooxygenase (COX) family of enzymes plays a crucial role in mediating inflammatory responses, and inhibition of COX-2 is a key

therapeutic target for controlling inflammation. In this study, VV-AgNPs exhibited a concentration-dependent effect on COX-2 expression (Fig. 8 & Table 2). The enzyme level increased significantly at 400 µg/mL (208.76 ± 18.86 µg/mL) compared with the control (128.90 ± 14.99 ng/mL), whereas lower concentrations (200–25 µg/mL) showed no significant difference. The observed increase at high concentrations may be attributed to oxidative stress induced by excess Ag⁺ ion release and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, which activate NF-κB and MAPK signaling pathways, leading to COX-2 upregulation. In contrast, at lower concentrations, the antioxidant activity of polyphenolic and flavonoid compounds adsorbed on the nanoparticle surface likely neutralizes ROS, maintaining redox balance and suppressing inflammatory signaling. Similar behavior was reported for *Solanum trilobatum*-derived AgNPs (IC₅₀ = 62.37 µg/mL) and *Mitragyna parvifolia* AgNPs (IC₅₀ = 53.09 µg/mL), which showed effective COX₂ inhibition compared with standard celecoxib (IC₅₀ = 37.36 µg/mL) [46,47]. The bi-duality property in VV-AgNPs also emphasizes the concentration-dependent phenomenon between the anti- and pro-inflammatory responses, thus validating the concept that higher amounts could produce mild cellular inflammation due to oxidative stress, rather than being biocompatible at higher levels.

Figure 8: Effect of VV-AgNPs on COX-2 enzyme expression at different concentrations

Table 2: Effect of VV-AgNPs concentration on COX-2 enzyme expression

Concentration (µg/mL)	VV-AgNPs	
	mean	SD
Control	128.9064	14.98828
400	208.7554	18.86143
200	179.541	9.38989
100	107.8327	25.55683
50	122.8441	21.31097
25	132.6015	25.14858

Antioxidant Activity of VV-AgNPs

The result of the DPPH assay showed that the biosynthesis of VV-AgNPs possessed a concentration-dependent radical scavenging ability with 73% scavenging efficiency at 500 µg/mL concentration, which is equivalent to the scavenging efficiency of ascorbic acid (75%) (Fig. 9). The antioxidant activities obtained in the present study were in concordance with the previously obtained results in the literature for AgNPs biosynthesized using plants, displaying a similar or higher antioxidant ability. Specifically, the scavenging efficiency for *A. bracteolata* AgNPs reached 79.16% at 100 µg/mL concentration, while AgNPs from *E. suberosa* extract had an IC₅₀ value of 30.04 µg/mL [48,49]. However, AgNPs from *corn* extract possessed a weaker activity (IC₅₀ = 385.87 µg/mL) [50]. The similarity between VV-AgNP values for VV Ag-NPs with ascorbic acid indicates high hydrogen- or electron-donating property values possibly attributed to phenolic molecules on the nanoparticle surface, which transfer their reducing power to the Ag core, stabilizing it while enhancing radical quenching through synergistic redox interactions.

Figure 9: VV-AgNPs antioxidant activity in comparison to ascorbic acid

Conclusion

The present research proved the successful eco-friendly biosynthesis of (VV-AgNPs) using *Vitis vinifera seed* extract as a biocompatible reducing agent. The biosynthesized nanoparticles possessed structural properties, in addition to showing remarkable antibacterial activities against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae* bacteria, but with reduced sensitivity against *P. aeruginosa* bacteria. Selective cytotoxicity was also demonstrated for VV-AgNPs on MCF-7 breast carcinoma cells with reduced impact on fibroblasts, in addition to safe anti-inflammatory action at lower doses, emphasizing that VV-AgNPs are stable biocompatible nanoparticles with notable bioactivity for possible microbial and anti-cancer applications.

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